

Evaluation of anti-inflammatory activity of *Acalypha indica* L. leaf extract using in vivo inflammation model

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ABSTRACT

The study aim to evaluate the anti-inflammatory effect of *Acalypha indica* L. in experiment animals. Methods: The methods of phytochemical screening of ethanolic extract of *Acalypha indica* L. leaves were including alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, sterols, glycosides and terpenoids. Phytochemical compounds were identified using GC-MS analysis. A plethysmometer was used to measure the volume of each rat's left hind paw after 0.1 mL of 1% w/v carrageenan was injected into the sub-plantar area to cause inflammation. *Acalypha indica* L. extract (AE) was administered orally to test group rats at 200 and 400 mg/kg. Diclofenac is administered intraperitoneally as a conventional medication at a dose of 10 mg/kg. Results: Oral administration of *Acalypha indica* L. extract at doses of 200 mg/kg and 400 mg/kg resulted insignificant reductions in paw volume by 71.98% ($P < 0.001$) and 77.95% ($P < 0.01$), respectively, after three hours. These effects were compared with the standard drug diclofenac (10 mg/kg, i.p.), which produced a 76.87% ($P < 0.01$) reduction in paw volume. Conclusion This study supports the potential of *Acalypha indica* L. as a source of effective herbal, plant-based anti-inflammatory agents and highlights the need for further research to identify the exact mechanisms of its active phytochemical components.

Keywords: Anti-inflammatory, Paw edema, *Acalypha indica* L., Carrageenan, Inflammation.

INTRODUCTION

The localized reaction of tissues to damage brought on by a variety of dangerous substances is called inflammation. It is a defensive reaction by the body aimed at eliminating or containing the harmful agent, followed by removing necrotic cells and tissues. Immune cells that have been shown to have an impact on the development of an inflammatory response include neutrophils, lymphocytes, dendritic cells, macrophages, and others.^[1] Different types of inflammatory reactions in the body lead to the production of various inflammatory mediators, including both pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory molecules. There are various molecules that play a crucial role in the body's inflammatory response, including interleukins, prostaglandins, leukotrienes, interferons, and tumor necrosis factor.^[2] Certain factors such as an excess of free radicals, the activation of complex enzymes, and the production of

pro and anti inflammatory mediators, can intensify acute inflammatory reactions.

Factors such as overcrowding of free radicals, complicated enzyme activation, and the producing of pro and anti-inflammatory mediators can intensify acute inflammatory reactions.^[3] Inflammation, pain, and platelet aggregation are caused by the synthesis of prostaglandins, prostacyclin, and thromboxane, is a primary function of the cyclooxygenase enzyme (COX). Recently, the primary treatments for various inflammatory diseases have been non-steroidal and steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs. However, prolonged usage of these drugs can lead to side effects including kidney failure, damage to the gastrointestinal tract, and ulcers in the stomach.^[4] It is crucial to develop anti-inflammatory medications that are non-toxic, safe, and effective.

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Plants have been used for centuries in Ayurvedic, Siddha, and Unani medicine to produce phytochemicals that have various medicinal uses.^[5] *calypha indica* L. belongs to the Euphorbiaceae family, commonly recognized as the spurge family. Other names of it includes Three-seeded mercury, Indian acalypha, Indian copperleaf, Indian nettle, and Indian mercury.^[6] With anti-diabetic, anti-venom, anti-bacterial, hepatoprotective, anti-cancer, hypoxic, anti-obesity, wound-healing, anti-hyperlipidemic, and anthelmintic properties, *Acalypha indica* L. is a powerful plant.^[7] Traditionally *Acalypha indica* L. used as an anti-inflammatory. Experimental establishment of the claim may prove beneficial for the society by introducing an effective alternative. *Acalypha indica* L. has been recognized by locals as a medicinal herb with numerous therapeutic benefits.^[8]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Drugs and chemicals

Drugs and chemicals	Manufacturer
Ethanol	Ecochem Ltd, Lichfield Street, Christchurch
Carrageenan	Sigma Aldrich, USA
Diclofenac	Zim Laboratories Ltd.

Collection and extraction procedure

Fresh leaves of *Acalypha indica* L. were collected from CIPT & A.H.S, Uluberia, Howrah. The plant was authenticated by Scientist E, K. Karthigeyan, at the Central National Herbarium, Botanical Survey of India, Howrah. Following several days of shade drying at room temperature, the gathered plant material was coarsely ground and sieved through a 40-mesh screen. The powdered material was defatted using petroleum ether for seventy two hours. Subsequently, approximately 80 grams of the defatted powder was subjected to ethanol extraction using a Soxhlet apparatus, yielding 12.5% (w/w) of the extract. The dried extract was refrigerated and kept in an airtight container.

Phytochemical screening

The ethanolic extract of *Acalypha indica* L. leaves were found to contain a variety of phytoconstituents

including alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, sterols, glycosides, and terpenoids, are shown in (Table 1).^[9]

Animals

For the experiment, healthy inbred Wistar rats weighing 180–220 grams were employed. The animals were kept in a controlled environment with a 12-hour light/dark cycle, a temperature of 23 ± 2 °C, and a relative humidity of $50 \pm 5\%$. They were housed in polypropylene cages with bedding made of sterile rice husk, fed a regular pellet diet, and given unlimited access to water. The rats were given a week to get used to the lab environment before the experiment started. Every experimental technique was authorized by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (IAEC) and carried out in compliance with the Committee for the Purpose of Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals (CPCSEA) rules, which are overseen by the Department of Animal Welfare, Government of India.

Acute oral toxicity studies

The rats fasted overnight before the drugs were administered. After that, a single oral dosage of an ethanolic extract of *Acalypha indica* L. leaves at a rate of 2000 mg/kg body weight was given. After administration, meals was not allowed for another three to four hours.

Every animal was examined separately at least once in the first half hour after the drug was administered, and then at regular intervals for the next twenty-four hours, paying particular attention to the first four hours. After that, for 14 days, the animals were observed every day.

Throughout the observation period, the rats were closely monitored for any behavioural or neurological changes, including signs such as drowsiness, restlessness, writhing, tremors, convulsions, or other symptoms of toxicity. Mortality, if any, was recorded throughout the two-week observation period.^[10]

Experimental design

Four groups of five animals each were randomly selected from among the experimental animals, and each group received the appropriate treatment:

Group I: Normal control (normal saline).

Group II: Test group *Acalypha indica* L. extract (AE) (200 mg/kg; p.o).

Group III: Test group *Acalypha indica* L. extract (AE) (400 mg/kg; p.o).

Group IV: Standard group Diclofenac (10 mg/kg; i.p).

Each rat's left hind paw's sub-plantar area received an injection of 0.1 mL of 1% w/v carrageenan solution.^[11,12,13] Using a Plethysmometer, the injected foot's swelling was measured at 0, 1, 2, and 3 hours, shown in Table 3. An hour before the carrageenan injection, the animals were given the test extract. The measurements were taken just before and three hours after the injection of carrageenan.^[14,15,16] The percentage of inhibition for the test drug was determined by comparing them with the vehicle control (100%).

Plethysmometer

The digital plethysmometer serves as an essential tool for evaluating inflammatory responses in small rodents and assessing the anti-inflammatory or anti-edema effects of test compounds. It operates by measuring the volume of water displaced when the animal's paw is immersed in the measuring tube, with the displacement volume displayed in a secondary

tube. The control unit can be reset between readings using a dedicated reset key, minimizing potential errors from residual water adhering to the paw. Additionally, a foot switch allows for efficient, hands-free operation, enabling precise control of the measurement endpoint and facilitating smooth, rapid data collection.

Statistical analysis

Each group will include five animals, and the results will be shown as Mean \pm (SEM) for each group. Dunnett's multiple comparison test will be used after one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) for statistical comparisons between groups. GraphPad Prism software was used for all analyses, and a p-value of less than 0.05 is regarded as statistically significant.

RESULTS

Acute oral toxicity

The extract was deemed safe in the LD₅₀ testing at a maximal dosage of 2000 mg/kg body weight, with no observable changes in normal behavioural patterns, without any sign of toxicity or mortality. Based on these findings, the biological evaluation was conducted at dose levels of 200 mg/kg and 400 mg/kg body weight.^[17]

Phytochemical Screening

Table 1. Phytochemical screening of *Acalypha indica* L. leaves

Sl No.	Name of the Test	Ethanollic Extract	
1	Test for sterols	Liebermann Reaction	+
2	Test for glycosides	Keller – Killiani Test	-
		Legal test	+
3	Test for saponins	Haemolytic test	-
		Foam test	-
4	Tests for proteins	Ninhydrin test	+
		Millon's test	-
5	Test for tannins	Gelatin test	+
		Ferric chloride test	+
6	Test for alkaloids	Dragendroff's test	-
		Mayer's test	+
7	Test for carbohydrates	Molisch's test	+
		Benedict's test	-
8	Test for Triterpenoids	Liebermann Burchard t's Test	+
		Salkowaski Test	-
9	Test for flavonoids	Lead acetate test	+
10	Test for Lipids	Sudan III reagent	+

(+) indicates presence, and (-) indicates absence

Fig. 1 Phytochemical screening results of *Acalypha indica* L. leaves.

Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) Analysis:

The analysis of ethanolic extract of *Acalypha indica* L. leaf was performed at Central Instruments Facility,

National Institute of Pharmaceutical Education and Research, Guwahati (NIPER - G), using Intuvo 9000GC System & 5977B GC/MSD, Agilent.

Fig. 2 Chromatograms of *Acalypha indica* L. extract (AE).

The GC-MS chromatogram of the *Acalypha indica* L. extract identified five phytochemical constituents associated with anti-inflammatory activity. The phytochemical compounds were α -D-Ribofuranose, Benzeneacetic acid, 3,4-Dihydroxy-5-methyl-

dihydrofuran-2-one, 1,1'-Biphenyl, 4,4'-dinitro and 3-Hydroxybenzoic acid. A number of bioactive compounds were identified in the *Acalypha indica* L. extract by GC-MS analysis, indicating the relevance to the current plant research.

Table 2. Bioactive compound of *Acalypha indica* L. extract (AE) by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry analysis.

SI No.	RT	Compound Name	Structure	Activity	Area Sum %
1	27.126	α -D-Ribofuranose		anti-inflammatory	0.09
2	20.466	Benzeneacetic acid		anti-inflammatory	0.01
3	24.433	3,4-Dihydroxy-5-methyl-dihydrofuran-2-one		anti-inflammatory	0.04
4	9.250	1,1'-Biphenyl, 4,4'-dinitro		anti-inflammatory	0.04
5	28.477	3-Hydroxybenzoic acid		anti-inflammatory	0.17

Table 3. Effect of *Acalypha indica* L. extract (AE) on the percentage inhibition of volume of inflammation

Parameter	Dose mg/kg	Volume of inflammation (ml)				% Inhibition after 180 min
		0 min	60 min	120 min	180 min	
Normal Control (Group I)	Normal Saline	28.41±1.74	69.56±1.43	88.34±1.51	136.59±1.34	----
<i>Acalypha indica</i> L. extract (Group II)	200	26.21±1.11	41.56±1.66*	49.66±1.81**	38.26±1.43***	71.98
<i>Acalypha indica</i> L. extract (Group III)	400	29.43±1.26	33.41±1.17**	38.26±1.84**	30.11±1.67**	77.95
Diclofenac (Group IV)	10	25.91±1.66	30.56±1.89**	33.41±1.99**	31.49±1.99**	76.87

For groups of five animals each (n = 5), the values are shown as Mean \pm (SEM). *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, and ***p < 0.001 denote statistical significance in relation to the normal control group.

Fig 3: Effect of *Acalypha indica* L. extract (AE) on edema volume (ml) of carrageenan induced paw edema.

DISCUSSION

The results of the current investigation on the anti-inflammatory properties of *Acalypha indica* L. ethanol extract in carrageenan-induced paw edema show that the extract effectively and considerably lowers swelling and inflammation^[18,19]. At three hours, the group of animals given 200 mg/kg of *Acalypha indica* L. extract showed a 71.98% decrease in paw volume, while those treated with 400 mg/kg had a 77.95% reduction. The plant extract has an anti-inflammatory effect ($P < 0.01$; $P < 0.001$) when compared to Diclofenac 10mg/kg, it resulted in a 76.87% reduction in paw volume. GC-MS analysis exhibits the presence of α -D-Ribofuranose, Benzeneacetic acid, 3,4-Dihydroxy-5-methyl-dihydrofuran-2-one, 1,1'-Biphenyl, 4,4'-dinitro and 3-Hydroxybenzoic acid which are associated with anti-inflammatory activity. The hind paw swelling caused by carrageenan is a commonly used model for researching acute inflammation. It is commonly employed to evaluate anti-inflammatory drugs because it does not elicit an immune response and has minimal systemic effects. Additionally, this model is highly reproducible.^[20,21]

There are two stages to swelling caused by carrageenan. Histamine, serotonin, and kinins are among the chemicals produced during the initial phase. Prostaglandins and slow-reacting chemicals are released during the second phase, peaking three hours after induction. Drugs like diclofenac, hydrocortisone, phenylbutazone, and indomethacin have been shown to effectively treat the edema during the second phase.^[22,23]

CONCLUSION

This study looked into the anti-inflammatory effects of the *Acalypha indica* L. as claimed by ethnomedicinal practice and GC MS analysis showed the presence of few chemical constituents responsible for anti-inflammatory action. The preliminary study results seem to be promising in terms of anti-inflammatory activity induced by carrageenan in an animal model. Further research is required to identify the exact mechanisms of action and carefully evaluate to establish the natural product as a better substitute of available anti-inflammatory drugs.

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